

Patient Data and Privacy in the Realm of Extended Reality: A Digital Health Perspective

Dr Rahul Sheshan Clare^{1,3*}[0009-0002-1820-6368], Dr Vani Lakshmi R²[0000-0003-2473-5311], Dr Asha Kamath²[0000-0003-0727-8067], Dr Sucheta V Kolekar³[0000-0003-2642-6088], Dr Poornima P Kundapur⁴[0000-0002-8271-524X]

¹Centre for Digital Health and Technologies, Prasanna School of Public Health, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, India- 576 104

²Department of Data Science, Prasanna School of Public Health, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, India- 576 104

³Department of Information and Communication Technologies, Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, India- 576 104

⁴Department of Data Science and Computer Applications, Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, India- 576 104
rahul.clare@manipal.edu

*Corresponding author

Abstract. The post-COVID-19 era has witnessed a wave of change in the generic patient-doctor interactions. Healthcare systems have been embedded with multi-layered technologies in compliance with the Sustainable Development Goals of the World Health Organization. The transformation towards technology adaptation is seen across an array of interconnected and interoperable systems, which includes tele-consultancy (including telemedicine), application of Internet of Things-based devices, digital diagnostics, digital therapeutics, mobile health applications (mHealth), electronic health applications (eHealth), clinical decision support systems, and technologies such as augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), mixed reality (MR); all of which fall within the purview of extended reality (XR).

The past year has witnessed several milestone legislations in the context of data privacy and AI, including the White House bill for AI, the Digital Personal Data Protection Act of India, the European Union AI reforms, and several amendments by OECD countries. However, a multitude of issues are seen in AI-based healthcare privacy and policies [1]. Unlike individuals who require passports or visas to cross international borders, data crossing and passage corridors are weak, and few have non-conformed borders/limitations. In the current era of deep learning seen in AI-generated images, deep fakes, voice makeovers, and gait replication, data privacy in patient data is perilous. What is more concerning is the fact that individuals have limitations in responding to privacy-related system glitches. The fearful aspect is when an individual's private details, down to the minute genetic chromosome, are shared with an unknown random for which the outcomes and misuse of data may have no limits. There is

not much focus on the intimate data captured by XR devices. XR is extensively used in the health sector, especially in the management of anxiety [2], dementia [3], depression, mental (psychiatric rehabilitation), physiotherapy and pain management [4], and post-traumatic stress disorder. AR/VR technologies have been mainly developed for gaming, simulated training, and educational purposes. The present study focuses on data privacy in the context of XR-based applications in healthcare. The study presents findings from a scoping review encompassing all the existing policies in this area of specialization. The study also carries out an extensive risk assessment of the existing policy frameworks for XR-based applications in healthcare and proposes the need for privacy impact assessment at micro/macro levels. The study offers an evidence-based approach to developing a framework for data privacy in the context of XR-based applications, which will enable policy-makers, researchers, and academia to have a fresh perspective on data privacy.

Keywords: Data Privacy, Policy, Patient, Extended-reality.

1 Introduction

1.1 Information and Communications Technology in Health

Digitization and Digitalization began penetrating the health sectors as part of monitoring and capturing data and has now grown at an incredible rapid phase. The once highly regarded concept of doctor-patient interactions wherein discussions, empathy, emotions, the process of self-evaluation, and judgements are in the process of being replaced by Artificial Intelligence (AI)-assisted clinical decision-making. Digital tools such as clinical support decisions, telehealth, digital therapeutics, m-health/e-health, and gamification including extended reality technologies (XRT) are on the rise in the current digital era. Digital data is one of the core foundations for the progressive development of systems including that of health technologies, their assessment, and the creating of diagnostic tools. Data privacy policy is a legal format which is integrated in any form of 'network' (intranet/internet) connected device a person may use.

The present era is governed by data, proofs, and validity along with undeniable fact that data needs to be shared among healthcare professionals and product developers for the purpose of continuous improvements, patient safety, risk mitigation, and research. Unlike precious metals, stones, or land, a 'data' is intangible, which makes it more valuable and fearful. While nations design data privacy policy to safeguard its national interest including the economy. Every nation's most important resource are its citizens for whom data privacy is as an armour which has an individuals' desire to protect, reveal, and limit the extent of personal information shared with others or stored in any form of medium (e.g. server, drive). Data privacy and policies are also designed to

provide a structural framework within which software developers can function seamlessly within a boundary. Data capturing and sharing of patient data for purposes other than which has been explained to the patients could lead to an even greater harm to the patient and the national security. Internet of Things (IoT) are physical devices/products which are connected to internet which has the ability to leverage an improved way of productivity. Some of the examples of IoT enabled devices in healthcare are mHealth/eHealth technologies, robot-assisted surgery, telemedicine, and XRT games.

1.2 Extended Reality in Healthcare

XRT is an umbrella term which incorporates Augmented Reality (AR), Mixed Reality (MR), and Virtual Reality (VR) technologies come under [5]. XRT has been considered as futuristic enabler in education, interconnectivity, operational work, and in treatment of certain mental health conditions. XRT with a few exceptions of AR and MR technologies (base model/earlier systems) are IoT enabled devices. XRT-Gamification in healthcare have benefited patients as well as healthcare professionals by means of cost effectiveness, ease of use (plug and play), portability, remote access, and can be used when required. The advancement in technologies involving gaming techniques could enhance the skills and training of healthcare workers while improves patient participation, and have effective outcomes. XRT is being extensively used in the healthcare sector especially in management of anxiety, dementia, depression, mental (psychiatric rehabilitation), physiotherapy and pain-management, and post-traumatic stress disorder. VR is also beneficial in managing stress in users including both healthcare providers and patients [6, 7]. Through gamification, patients can undergo behavioural changes, manage their chronic illnesses, and experience motivation to follow their treatment. Some of the examples include Fitbit, an application that tracks the physical fitness of the user and persuades them to meet their diet and exercise goals; GestureTek Health looks at physical therapy and rehabilitation, especially for mental health hospitals, disabled, and education domain; and Re-Mission that aids children deal with cancer through games [8]. Given the numerous health related benefits of XRT-games for patients, there is a lack of data privacy awareness among patients on the uses and misuses of data being shared.

1.3 Extended Reality in Healthcare: Risks and Challenges

Most of the IoT enabled devices we use are embedded with artificial intelligence and machine learning modules. There is also a multitude of issues are seen in AI based healthcare privacy and policies including that of IoT enabled medical devices. Data captured by wearable health devices such as smart watch which is a form of augmented reality could be shared with third party such as insurance companies affecting the patients right for an insurance coverage. Renowned smart watch brands have strict policy (government and in-house), but the same could not be said for mediocre and cost effective brands. Failure in maintaining data privacy and security drastically affects mental health including social security. Data breach mentioned by Daly [9] as “data breaches

involve security breaches, which lead to the disclosure, access or acquisition of information” is among the cause of harm for patient. Unconsented sharing of data is also another cause of risk. Richter and Slowinski [10] defined data sharing as “data sharing includes all possible data flows between companies or customers”.

Another risk seen with the data collection and sharing is that associated with cookies, which are mandatory functional agreements without which software (web or mobile applications) do not function effectively. The non-acceptance of cookies usually results in operational challenges which curbs an individual’s freedom, restricts choices, paving the way for poor functioning of the application. The risk also increases when current and older data has been shared to groups, or organization, or individual outside the home country. With increased access to sophisticated Artificial Intelligence-Machine Learning (AI-ML), and quantum computing technologies, data sharing can prove to become a security threat at national and international levels.

AR/VR technologies have been mainly developed for gaming, simulated training, and educational purposes which includes those in healthcare sectors. Unfortunately, since these are still classified under games/gaming technologies, hence the data collected (personal and physical) does not fall under the regulatory aspects of health sector. The data collected by the XRT is not fully known to the user, and user interface needs improvisation. The fearful aspect is when an individual person private details down to the eye movement, gait, speech pattern could be shared to an unknown person for which the outcomes and misuse of data may have no limits. The standards for gaming rating depend on each country and the program developers. The suitable age requirement in the United Kingdom is year 12 and above, the Kingdom of Netherlands has established a criterion of age 16 and above. XR technology companies are subjected to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and ePrivacy Directive however certain challenges arise from these directives [11].

XRT has been called as a “dream machine” [12], for its immersive experience provided to the user. The importance of XRTs in the health sector can be highlighted with Apple watch receiving approval by the Food and Drug Administration under the Medical Device Development Tools program for its atrial fibrillation data while reducing the burden of an implantable device [13]. Another ground breaking development by Neuralink brain-chip showcasing its first chip implant patient controlling computer mouse to play chess using thoughts [14]. Both examples of XRT are highly commendable developments in healthcare sector, whilst highlighting the importance of a policy framework of XRT in healthcare.

Despite its potential to reshape the digital health ecosystem, XRT is marred by huge disparities in the regulatory landscape across the globe. With growing data privacy concerns, there is a need to examine the extent, range and nature of research in data privacy associated with XRT for digital health. Furthermore, it is pertinent to identify privacy gaps in research in the context of policy frameworks and regulatory landscapes across

countries and international organizations. In addition, there is a need to understand the risks unique to use of XRT in digital health; all of which form the crux of this work.

2 Methodology

The present study makes use of a scoping-review approach to seek answers to the underlying research questions specific to data privacy and risks in the context of XR in digital health. A scoping review is a unique form of systematic literature review introduced by [15]. According to the authors, “the scoping review could be used to address one or more of the following objectives:

- To examine the extent, range and nature of research activity
- To determine the value of undertaking a full systematic review
- To summarise and disseminate research findings
- To identify research gaps in the existing literature

For this scoping review, a systematic literature search in PubMed, Scopus and IEEE was carried out, focusing on full-text articles in English considering a five-year window (January 2019 to March 2024) using the search terms: “privacy”, “framework” with (“extended reality” OR “augmented reality” OR “mixed reality” OR “virtual reality”). The first two authors carried out the literature search independently in two different geographical locations, and the remaining contributors supported fine-tuning the article selection process, identification of appropriate use of Boolean operators. The search yielded 117 results (Scopus-84, PubMed-20 and IEEE-13) involving full-text articles in English. However, 9 articles were found to be appropriate for the study. After removing two duplicates, seven articles were shortlisted of which, 6 articles focussed on privacy by design and the seventh article detailed about privacy aspects in Metaverse. Additionally, an extensive search of regulatory and legal aspects in the context of healthcare across multiple countries was carried out and the findings from the same have been summarized in Tables 1-2.

Fig. 1. Steps in a Scoping Review [16]

However, there is no assumption that the evidence reviewed is exhaustive. The articles were subsequently discussed through consensus between the researchers. Fig. 1 presents the steps undertaken by the researchers in carrying out the review. The data extraction was carried out by first screening the title, followed by the abstract and the full text in the same order of sequence. Microsoft Excel 2016 was used to summarize the data and tabulate the article-related information by the authors.

3 Results

The section presents the findings from the scoping review and is presented in a tabular format highlighting XR-specific findings across the data protection policies across the countries. Several international organizations have proposed policies to ensure that the patient privacy is protected. The findings from the same has been highlighted in Table 2. Table 3 presents a summary of crucial risks associated with XR.

3.1 Data Privacy Regulations across the Globe: Countries and International Organizations

Table 1. Summary of Data Privacy Regulations across the Globe with XR specific findings

	Country	Year	Description	Limitations	XR-specific findings
ASIA	China	2021	Personal Information Protection Law (PIPL) focuses on protecting the personal data of Chinese citizens. Requires data localization and government oversight [17].	Limited transparency and due process around enforcement actions. Concerns around data localization hindering international data flows.	Lack of guidelines, policy or regulatory information
		2022	Virtual Reality and Industry Application Integration Development Action Plan (2022 - 2026)		
	Thailand	2019	Personal Data Protection Act (PDPA): Similar to GDPR, it grants individuals control over personal data [18].	The relatively new law, with enforcement mechanisms still under development.	Lack of information
	South Korea	2011	Personal Information Protection Act (PIPA): Regulates the collection, use, and disclosure of personal information [19].	Focus on self-regulation and potential for weak enforcement.	Does not discuss about privacy challenges associated with XR.
		2023	Data transparency and control in XR and the Metaverse	A consultancy report based out of private entities from Singapore and South Korea.	These two programs were motivated by the desire to discover insights that can help products and policy-makers create people-centered approaches to designing XR experiences and the metaverse, in South Korea and Singapore. Co-design is a collaborative practice that encourages diverse stakeholders to work together to develop products, services, or policy solutions.

	Japan	2003	Act on the Protection of Personal Information (APPI) requires data controllers to obtain consent and imposes security safeguards [20].	Limited enforcement mechanisms and potential for conflicting interpretations.	Ongoing research in the existing GDPR, medical device sector.
	India	2023	Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 takes a giant leap from Information Technology Act, 2000 to provide a comprehensive data protection mechanism.	The Act is yet to be enforced. Limitations include extensive state control, consent issues, government immunity, and compromised independence.	The Act is perhaps the first regulation to make a mention on XR based data privacy concerns
EU	European Union (EU)	2016	General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) sets a high bar for data protection, granting individuals extensive rights to access, control, and delete their data [21].	It is complex and costly to comply with, especially for smaller businesses. Creates challenges for data transfers outside the EU. It also has principles for Data minimization.	Article 22 of the GDPR offers minimal baseline guidelines in data privacy for XRT [22] .
AMERICAS	US	2023	Triggers when AI processes use personal data. The data controller and AI/ML system have to be from the EU. Data retention period, and a data processing agreement. Does not share data to unsafe countries.	AI/ML system has to be from EU nations which could be disadvantageous to software developed outside EU.	Lack of guidelines, policy, or regulatory information. The policy is vague and open ended leading to uncertainties, and possibility of financial implications.
		(2018, 2023)	No single federal law. Several sectoral and state-level laws exist, including the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) and the Virginia Consumer Data Protection Act (VCDPA).	A patchwork of laws creates confusion and inconsistency for businesses operating across state lines. Lacks the comprehensive nature of the GDPR.	Not available.
		1938	FDA	Authorize the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) to oversee and regulate the production, sale, and distribution of food, drugs, medical devices, and cosmetics	Not available.

		1946	Federal Tort Claims Act	Waived the sovereign immunity of the United States for certain acts or omissions by federal employees occurring within the scope of their employment	Not available.
		2023	Federal Trade Commission Health Breach Notification Rule- 16 CFR Part 318	Requires companies that experience a breach of security of consumers' identifying health information to notify affected consumers, the FTC, and, in some cases, the media	Not available.
		1996	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). Is protected by Federal guidelines, and respects individual privacy via "Protected Health Information"	Is cumbersome due to complex compliance requirements which also reduces the pace of innovative products/processes.	Not available
		2018	California Consumer Protection Act (CCPA) has right to data, and how data is shared.	It also has right to delete data with minor exceptions, the right to opt out. The 2023 amendment includes the right to rectify erroneous data.	Not available

	Brazil	2020	General Data Protection Law (GDPL): Inspired by the GDPR, it grants individuals rights to access, rectify, and delete their data [23].	Relatively new law, with evolving interpretations and enforcement practices.	Gaming companies including XRT within and outside Brazil offering games accessible in the country must adhere to the LGPD. Whether processing personal data in Brazil, offering services to Brazilian individuals, or collecting data within Brazil, the rules of GDPL apply, which includes prioritize minors' interests when processing their data, and using specific mechanisms for cross-border data transfers.
	Canada	2000	Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA): A federal law with some limitations on scope and enforcement [24].	Limited scope to personal information held by specific organisations (e.g. commercial entities) and considered less stringent than GDPR.	No discussion on privacy in XR.

Organization	Document	Year	Description and XR-specific comments	Limitations
WHO (WHO Members)	WHO Strategy for Digital Health (2020-25)	2021	WHO wishes to promote the sharing of health data, including but not restricted to surveillance and epidemiological data. Applies to the use and sharing of data collected by WHO in, and/or provided to WHO by, Member States, outside the context of public health emergencies. The policy allows, but places no obligation on, WHO or Member States to collect, anonymize, analyze, or share other health data than those already being collected, anonymized, analyzed, and shared.	Enforcement of the policies and its implementation is a challenge. In addition,
	WHO Data Policy	2017		
IMDRF (Members of the Forum)	International Medical Device Regulators Forum	2011	A voluntary group of medical device regulators which includes the FDA as a part of management committees. It also encompasses the list of software functions, some of which may not meet the definition of a device in Section 201(h) of the FDCA. Possible relevance to 'software as a medical device' (SaMD) along with the inclusion of the 'Essential principles of safety and performance of the medical device and In-vitro diagnostic medical device'	Implementation and participation challenges. Reporting and classification challenges due to multiple stakeholders. device'
NIST	NIST	1901	Federal agency operating for over one hundred twenty years, specializing in measurement science, frameworks, operational standards, technology processes [21].	The relatively new law, with enforcement mechanisms still under development.
	NIST AI	2023	Focuses in improving measurement science, technology with a focus on standards and systems, tools and evaluation of data. January 23rd, 2023 was the launch of AI risk management framework, and version 2 on August 8th, 2023 which includes risk management for generative AI. NIST AI aligns to meet International requirements [22].	Human, Institutional, and systemic bias has been acknowledged by NIST AI. Implementation lags due to operational and societal constraints. Ongoing research in the field of XR for cybersecurity, visualization, IoT-enabled devices (human-robot interface), smart production, and fire data collection.
XRSI	Extended Reality Safety Initiative Framework	2003	The XR Safety Intelligence framework offers a robust approach to privacy and safety in immersive technologies. It harmonizes global privacy standards, underlining the criticality of informed consent and child safety. It advocates for proactive privacy measures like content moderation and anonymization.	Poor industry adoption and enforcement challenges at industry and regional levels.
OECD (Applicable to OECD members)	Privacy protection legislation	1971	Inspired by the privacy protection legislation in Sweden (1969)-reported in 1972, which resulted in the world's first data protection laws in 1973.	Implementation in national and regional zones, cross-border data sharing in terms of

				consent, justification, and transparency.
	Council of Europe: Ministerial Resolution (Convention No 108)	1973 -74	Addresses challenges automated personal data processing.	
	Data Protection Rules	1980 (R1:2013 and R2:2022)	Require that personal data be processed in a transparent manner for legitimate purposes to deliver the relevant mission and work programme. Personal data are to be adequate, relevant, kept up-to-date, limited to what is needed and retained for no longer than necessary. The Rules also require that the responsible staff ensures that contractors processing personal data on OECD's behalf provide guarantees on the implementation of appropriate technical and organisational measures.	
	OECD Guidelines on the Protection of Privacy and Trans border Flows of Personal Data	1980	Report an international consensus on how best to balance effective privacy protection with the free flow of personal data. Technology-neutral, flexible, allow for various means of compliance, and apply in all environments, including on global networks. To be used in a large number of national regulatory and self-regulatory instruments and are still widely used in both the public and private sectors.	
	Principles on Artificial Intelligence	2019	A set of intergovernmental guidelines that has been recognized by 42 countries. Promote AI that is innovative and trustworthy and that respects human rights and democratic values	Country-specific regulations, and implementation challenges. Intellectual property, safety, and information integrity challenges.

3.2 Data Privacy Risks: Summary of Findings

Table 3. Summary of Data Privacy Risks in XR

SI No	Risk	Description	Use Cases
1	Technological Considerations	Privacy-by-Design: focusses on data protection through technology design ensuring visibility, transparency, respect for user privacy, end-to-end security across the functionality, and pro-active and preventative privacy, thus, facilitating user-centric design. Privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs): are a broad set of tools and methods aimed at providing ways to build products and functionality while protecting the privacy of user data. Some PET approaches include end-to-end encryption, differential privacy, and privacy-preserving federated learning.	Mobile devices can collectively train a model to improve voice recognition features, without sending user voice recordings to a server

2	Anonymity Considerations	<p>Socio-cultural and Demographic Identifiers: XR technologies often capture sensitive attributes which include gender, age, clinical characteristics of patients, cultural background, and facial attributes which leads to the failure of traditional data anonymization paradigms. Health Stigma and Discrimination: XR-based applications also capture mental health-related aspects (if designed for well-being and mental health), assessment of cognitive abilities, drug consumption-related data, skills, and abilities, and data on the daily routine of patients, to mention a few. Location privacy: XR-based applications often store spatial (i.e. location) data which will result in de-identification violations. This will also result in a violation of bystander/caregiver privacy. (https://arxiv.org/pdf/2307.12847)</p>	<p>A memory care patient requires assistance with identifying close friends and relatives. An application, using an AR device, identifies faces using facial recognition software and presents the names and/or titles of these persons to assist the user.</p>
3	Legal Aspects	<p>XR is Compliance and Regulatory Risks of data being shared is different from</p>	
4	Data Risks	<p>One of the most crucial concerns with the use of XR in healthcare is related to possible risks associated with third-party data sharing, cross-border privacy, questions on data ownership, and consent.</p>	<p>The US Food and Drug Administration recommends wise use of XR technologies [25].</p>
5	Health Risks	<p>Prolonged use of XR technologies has shown symptoms (not limited to) of cyber-sickness, which display signs similar to motion sickness, fatigue, eye strain, and radiation exposure. Prolonged use of immersive XR gaming which are choice-based games which are violent in nature could potentially lead to negative emotions, feeling of guilt, and at time desensitized to negative emotions [26].</p>	<p>Signs such as headache, nausea, and vomiting, are usually due to the immersive nature of AR/VR/XR. [27]</p>
6	Cybersecurity Risks	<p>Both financial data and biometric data (eye-tracking, head direction, hand position, bodily motion, facial recognition, fingerprint verification (Dactyloscopic data), Iris scanning, Retinal analysis, Voice recognition, and ear shape recognition) when captured by XR poses the risk of data breach leading (and not limited to) financial fraud [28, 29].</p>	<p>XR systems often require detailed sensitive data such as interpupillary distance to generate XR data [30]. Users are often not aware of these technical details that expose their identities. Identity theft can occur when this information is misused.</p>
7	Technical Risks	<p>This includes design vulnerabilities that will prevent the user from having a pleasant experience with the application; usability and user control concerns that will lead to a poor understanding of the utility of the XR application, poor error handling, and interoperability issues [31].</p>	<p>A study on interactions on four different XR platforms for a biomedical application revealed that even though these platforms have very different interaction capabilities, they can all be suitable for biomedical training tasks. However, if the interactions are not designed well, it can lead to a poor understanding of the utility of the XR application [32].</p>

5 Conclusion

As Sir Stephen Hawkins once mentioned “*Our future is a race between the growing power of Technology and the wisdom with which we use it*” [33]. Perhaps, it is this paradoxical thought has led most organizations including WHO to formulate their policy for data collection leading to privacy considerations in digital health technologies. The history of XR technologies began in 1838 via AR by Charles Wheaton as a mechanism mode to demonstrate virtual tourism, by the year 1965 Robert Mann used AR/VR systems for training in orthopaedic diagnostics, and by the late 1980’s HMDs were used in Medical training for students [34].

With alarming rise in the data breaches across the globe, data privacy has become one of the crucial touchpoints for research in XR for healthcare in recent years. Research in data privacy in XR is primarily centred on privacy-by-design approaches. While data protection has been a cornerstone of several healthcare data- related regulations across the globe as observed in this study, the XRSI is the first step in addressing the risks associated with privacy specific to XR. This scoping review calls for a need to formulate risk assessments and privacy impact assessments which could be tested in the validation phase of the development of an XR-based technology. There is also a need to assess gaps in evaluating XR devices that hinder regulatory assessment. Safety and effectiveness need further research across use cases. Improved evaluation practices and standards that support regulations across different countries will serve as a catalyst in expanding the possibilities of using XR to promote health and well-being while being wary of the potential challenges associated with over-reliance on XR.

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